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**NECESSITY OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT
IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS*****Vinutha, **Vranda**

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Abstract

India is the richest human capital country in the world. However enrolment in higher education is lower as compared to developed countries. It is a setback to take Indian economy on rapid economic growth path. Thus, in recent year's government of India paid highest attention to enhance enrolment ratio in higher education under NITHI AYOGA. The major difficulty is how to develop employability among graduates particularly in rural India. Keeping this in mind various levels of government introduced skill development training to improve the qualities of graduate of rural area. In this context this paper makes an attempt to highlight the necessity of various kinds of occasional training and skill development schemes within the framework of higher education institution. The paper suggests the government to integrate soft skill and job skill training with course curriculum of graduation and post graduation. The integration of training and development with course curriculum will improve the employability amongst rural people thereby channelize human resource to economic growth.

Keywords: Development, Higher education, Necessities, Training, Soft skill

1. INTRODUCTION

India is a country which has abundant human resource. Hence, the central and state government has a commitment of transferring this man power as human capital. The process of transformation human resource into human capital involves training and development. Training is a short-term and reactive activity which focuses on changing or improving the knowledge, skills and above all attitude of individuals to perform a particular job or task. From the two decades, training and development closely link human resource management, talent management, human resource development, institutional design, and knowledge management. The process of development in relation to insights, attitudes, adoptability, leadership and human relationship are most essential to enhance emotional quotient.

Unfortunately, the efforts of government towards training and development in higher education institutions are negligible and consequently, 5% of labour has occasional training in India. It is very low as compared to developed country like USA, China and Mexico. The adverse consequence of it is on productivity, health, safety and personal development of employee. Thus, the training on cross-cultural and new organisation development which relates to employment is very essential to make access population more productive.

In this context, various committee reports suggested government of India to undertake training and development activities within the course curriculum of higher education. The integration of training within higher education framework will enhance intelligent and emotional quotient of the students. An improvement in emotional quotient makes people of our nation more productive and sustainable. Therefore, this proposed study aims to evaluate a necessity of training and development activities in higher education institutions particularly in rural India.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

K.Ashwatappa (2008) - Training and Development improves performance of employee by changing his attitude

Rajendran Karuppanan (2012) - It reveals that training is necessary any to inculcate positive changes in knowledge skills and attitudes.

Vo and Hannif (2012) - Lack of vocational training in higher education cause to increase cost burden of employer for training.

Lorette (2018) - The training and development remains to nourish the skills of employees which help to accomplish the organisational goals.

The study relates to necessity of training and development in higher education institutes is very limited in Indian context. Hence this study is unique.

3. STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEM:

Soon after the globalisation, Indian higher education institutes gave emphasis to job oriented course curriculum. However, the changing pattern of food, culture and skills has adverse consequences on health and competence level of youth. Therefore leakages of human resource have been increasing in recent years. In this context integration of soft skills training within higher education frame work is very much essential to reduce leakages in human resource. The proposed study aims to evaluate necessity of training and development in higher education institutions.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- 1) To high light necessity of training and development in higher education.
- 2) To identify the challenges for integrating training and development programs within the frame work of higher education institution.

5. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

Sources of data:-As study deals with training and development in higher education particularly in rural area, the data's are collected from primary source of information.

Sample size: - Study covers 50 respondents of sample unit.

6. DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES:

The study uses pie square and ratio analysis techniques to analyse data.

TRAINING ATTENDED (%)

Author’s calculation:

In the given chart 42% of respondent participated in personality development (soft skill and life skill training).22% respondent took occasional training .16% of respondent got job skill training. 20% of respondent have undergone corporate training. Therefore the finding of the study reveals that the awareness of occasional training and some job oriented training is very limited in rural area.

METHOD OF GETTING JOB TRAINING (%)

Author’s calculation:

In the analysis, 16% of respondent willing to attend on the job training, 22% like to take off the job training and 62% suggested on the job and off the job training.

NUMBER OF TRAINING SESSION ATTENDED (%)

Author’s calculation:

In the survey, 44% of students have attended maximum 2 training sessions. 28% of students attended 3 training sessions.14% of students attended 4 training sessions .and 14% of students participated in more than 5 training sessions. This finding suggest education institution to create awareness on the relevance of soft skill and job skill training in cultivating employability among graduates of rural area.

PERCEPTION OF STUDENTS ON TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

DESCRIPTION	PERCENTAGE OF STUDENTS	
	YES	NO
Necessity of training on employability	88	12
Regularity of training process in college	54	46
Training enhances confidence level	86	14
Positive influence of training on personality	70	30

Author

’s calculation:

In the given data analysis 88% students highlighted necessity of training in education institutions to develop competency amongst graduates in rural area. In the survey 54% of students have undergone capacity enhancement programme on regular basis training process. 86% of trainings have developed their self confidence through soft skill education. In the total number of trainings 70% of them find positive effects of training in their personality development.

7. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The main focus of the study is to empower rural people through training and development. The integration of training and development in the course curriculum of higher education will increase productivity of education institution. Also, the performance of employee will be increased .The ultimate impact of inclusion of training and development in higher education is minimisation in leakage of human resource. Therefore, this study throws light on how training and development in higher education will influence human resource development and economic growth.

8. LIMITATIONS:

As training and development in higher education newly introduced concept, the awareness on it is very limited among students of rural area. Hence, the collection of data in relation to training and development is problematic task.

9. CONCLUSION:

In the rural area, most of the students are first generation graduates. Hence they are not aware of contribution of training programmes in personality development. Thus, this paper suggests government to formulate policy on soft skill and job skill training in the course curriculum of higher education.

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